

Table 1.1. Overview of SOILCARE Study Sites

Study Site	Type of crop	Intensity cropping *	Soil improving cropping systems and techniques currently used	Pedo-climatic zone ^{&}	Problem that causes yield loss or increased cost	Availability of long-term data
1. Flanders, BE	Food crops (winter wheat, sugar beet, potato), vegetables, forage, orchards	C, CO, O	Minimised input & tillage, rotation, cover crops, organic amendments	Atlantic Central, soil depends on site	N and P leaching, erosion, compaction, SOC [#]	From 1997: 14 compost treatments, 2002: Reduced tillage
2. Akershus, NO	Cereals	T, CO	Reduced tillage, sludge & biochar, increase C, precision fertilization	Nemoral/Boreal, marine clay soils	Erosion, nutrient loss, pests, disease, SOC, compaction	1991: tillage methods, 1977: Reduced tillage
3. Keszthely, HU	Annual: cereals, maize	C, CO	Rotations, intercropping, green-manure, mulching, minimum tillage	Pannonian, brown forest soils	Soil compaction, humus degradation, nitrate leaching, acidity, weeds	1964, 1969, 1972, 1984: 2 factorial field experiments
4. Frauenfeld, CH	Grass, cereals, maize, rape, potato, sugar beet, vegetables	C, CO	Mouldboard ploughing, no-tillage, burial crop residues, large tyres	Continental/Alpine South, Fluvisol	Soil structure, subsoil compaction, pounding risk	Mechanization level : 12 years; fuel consumption: 3 years
5. Viborg, DK	Winter cereals (wheat, 25%) and forage crops	C, O, P	Fertilizer norms, rotations, minimum tillage, incorporation straw, cover crops	Atlantic North, sandy-loamy soils.	SOC, Compaction, erosion, nutrient losses (N and P)	Askov: Rotation, fertilisation, > 120 years St. Jydevad (1942): 16 combis of lime, P
6. Loddington, GB	Cereals, oilseeds, pulses, grass/clover leys	CO, P	Rotation, minimum tillage, cover crops, bio-compost, residues returned.	Atlantic Central/North, clay soils	Compaction, SOC	20 years soil nutrient status. Access to Rothamsted data (since 1843)
7. Tachenhausen, DE	Maize, wheat, barley, rape, soya	C	No tillage, cover crops, measure to increase C in soils	Atlantic Central, karst, silty loam	Soil structure, compaction, reduced infiltration	Crop management, organic agriculture, soil tillage, soil cover
8. Draganesti Vlasca, RO	Annual food crops – cereals, sunflower	C, CO	Rotation, minimised tillage	Pannonian, Phaeozem	Soil compaction	10 years: different tillage systems
9. Legnaro, IT	Annual crops (maize, wheat, sugar beet, soybean, alfalfa)	C	Rotation, organic fertilisers (different types and amounts)	Mediterranean North, Cambisol	SOC, compaction, climate variations	96 different combinations of rotation, fertilisation (1962).
10. Szaniawy, PL	Barley, rye, wheat, oats, potatoes, maize, grassland.	T, C	Minimised input agricultural chemicals, legume crops, lime	Continental, Sandy, loamy soils	Water deficit, SOC, acidity, compaction, weeds.	Crop yield, soil water and soil temperature since 2001
11. Caldeirão, PT	Cereals (maize and rice), vineyards	C, O	Rotation, optimisation of irrigation	Lusitanian, silty-clayey soils	Water availability	Surveys since early 1990's
12. Chania, Crete, GR	Permanent: olive, citrus vineyards	T, C	Minimum input & tillage, manuring, precision irrigation, green strips	MediterraneanI South, Calcisol	Erosion, compaction, water availability	Inputs, costs and yield for over 10 years in various fields

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13. Orup, SE	Annual crops: winter wheat, spring barley, spring oilseed rape, peas	C	Loosening of upper subsoil and incorporation of organic material and lime	Nemoral, sandy loams	Compaction	Lanna: Yield data from 1982, 6 treatments Orup: Yields since 1957,32 treatments
14. Prague-Ruzyně, CZ	Barley, rye, wheat, oats, potatoes, maize, grassland	C, T, O	Minimum tillage, rotation, soil improving crops, erosion measures	Continental, Luvisol	Erosion, compaction, SOC, acidification, reduced water retention	Fertilisation (since 1956; 1056 plots), rotations (since 1971), tillage (since 1988)
15. Almeria, ES	Olive, grape, subtropical fruit crops, stone fruits	T, O	No-tillage, minimised tillage Cover crops	Mediterranean South, Regosol, Leptosol	Erosion, salinization	Literature data for olives
16. Brittany, FR	Wheat, maize, grassland	O	Biological pest management, green manure, organic fertilisers	Lusitanian/ Atlantic Central, Cambisol	Compaction, weeds	Management and yield data

#:SOC= Soil Organic Carbon decline; * C=Conventional, T=traditional, O=organic, CO=conservation, P=precision; & Climatic zones based on Metzger et al (2005)